

JOB CRAFTING AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE HEALTH

CREACIÓN DE TRABAJO Y SALUD DEL DESEMPEÑO ORGANIZACIONAL

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RESUMEN

Esta investigación tiene como objetivo determinar el efecto de la creación de trabajo en la salud del desempeño organizacional. Esta es una investigación aplicada. Los resultados mostraron que el liderazgo orientado a los empleados afecta positiva y significativamente la salud y el desempeño de los empleados y la promoción de la creación de empleos; sin embargo, su efecto en la prevención de la creación de empleos es negativo e insignificante.

Palabras clave: Creación de trabajo, desempeño organizacional, salud

ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the job crafting effect on organizational performance health. This is applied research. The results showed that employee-oriented leadership positively and significantly affects the health and performance of employees and job crafting promotion, however, its effect on the prevention of job crafting is negative and insignificant.

Keywords: Job Crafting, Organizational Performance, Health

Fecha de recepción: junio 2019

Fecha de aprobación: octubre 2019

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8115318>

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, and with a mindful restoration to the relevant opinions on leadership trait theories in a new framework, there has been a special motion under titles such as leadership attribution, charismatic leadership theory, servant leadership, super leadership, the transactional leadership theory and transformational leadership. One of the features of the recent theories is that they are trying to incorporate the factors which inspire individuals to perform in an effective way. Similar to management, leadership involves effectiveness, requiring work with people. Leadership and management both seek an effective realization of objectives, but they have also some differences (Rostami and Salari, 2018).

Among the leadership approaches there is the employee-oriented leadership. The employee-oriented leaders are supporting the employees through informational, emotional and instrumental methods related to individual needs and their welfare, trying to create the working conditions they can accomplish (Nielsen & Munir, 2017; Tuckey, Bakker & Dollard, 2016). Lichtenthaler & Fischbach (2018) suggest that the employee-oriented leadership is positively related to job crafting promotion, while it is negatively related to its prevention.

Job crafting is a new perspective introduced due to change in working dynamics, increased competitive pressures of the organization to attract and attain the qualified employees, for increased employee expectations for participation in working environment as well as searching for meaningful job conditions, emphasizing the active role of employees in job design (Naami and Shenavar, 2015). Generally, job crafting refers to a process in which the employee's number, type, obligation scope and communications in the job are changed in a way so as to fit their interests and capabilities.

Job crafting has three basic realms. In the first realm which is known as the change in the task boundaries, the individual changes the content, number and scope of his job assignments. The second realm which is known as communicational boundaries, suggests that the individual changes the type of its communications and interactions at the time of performing the designated tasks. The third realm is the realm of cognitive change of obligation boundaries which suggests the change in perspectives and his view towards the occupation (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2018; Naami and Shenavar 2015). In their research, Lichtenthaler & Fischbach (2018) concluded that the job crafting is a mediating factor in the effect of leadership style on the employee health and performance.

Performance is the final output criterion of an organization which is affected by numerous possibilities of market and organizational conditions and includes different aspects. The performance criterion is to improve the company's future performance. Business owners use performance in order to achieve company

objective goals. Today, every manager needs appropriate factors in order to improve their company.

RESEARCH LITERATURE

Job crafting is a major challenge for the survival and success of an organization because it directs the performance and job satisfaction of its employees (Rostami and Salari, 2018). The job performance of an individual is very important for organizational survival and can be considered as the most important result of work and job satisfaction. All jobs are important, so they are one of the main goals of the organization, and organizations must provide the conditions to keep employees satisfied (Naami and Shenavar, 2015).

Although job performance has always been a problem in organizations, job performance is an emotional and positive state resulting from job evaluation or work experience that has various dimensions and factors. Most traditional models that focus on job performance focus on how a person feels about their job, but what shapes job satisfaction is not the nature of the profession, but the expectations one has of the job (Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2018).

Rostami and Salari (2018) conducted a study titled the relationship between leadership styles and organizational performance by considering the mediating role of HR strategy (Case study: The employees of Toos Mashhad Industrial Township). The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between leadership styles and organizational performance by considering the mediating role of HR strategies. The results show that there is a significant role between leadership styles and organizational performance among the employees of Toos Mashhad Industrial Township by considering the mediating role of human resource strategies.

Hypothesis test results showed that the job engagement, job involvement, education, development and support of managers had direct and significant effect on job performance of faculty members. There was no significant difference between job engagement and job performance. Among this, job engagement with path coefficient of 0.32 had a significant effect on job performance and job involvement with the path coefficient of 0.18 had the lowest effect on job performance.

ShabaniNejad, Alvari & Georgi (2016) conducted an investigation entitled the relation between transformational leadership and job performance at Farabi hospital. The purpose of this study was to identify the relationship between transformational leadership and job performance of employees in Farabi. The results of the correlation test showed that there is a significant relationship between

the transformational elements of the transformational leadership and employee job performance. The correlation coefficient for each of the transformational leadership elements led to an ambitious influence (59%), inspirational motivation (48%), subjective persuasion (56%), and individual considerations (43%). Also, when reviewing the simultaneous effect of transformational leadership dimensions on job performance using multiple regression, it showed that ideal influence variables and subjective persuasion had 42% and 39% positive effect on employee job performance, respectively.

Naami and Shenavar (2015) conducted a research entitled role of job enthusiasm, job control, innovative behavior, and transformational leadership in predicting job transformation. The aim of this study was to determine the role of job enthusiasm, job control, innovative behavior, and transformational leadership with a change of job satisfaction. The results showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction, job control, innovative behavior and transformational leadership. Furthermore, the results of the regression analysis showed that among the variables, job enthusiasm, innovative behavior and transformational leadership have a major role in explaining the variance of job transformation.

Baharloo, Mahmoudi Kia and Ahmadi Chageni (2016) investigated the relationship between dynamic personality and job performance with job transformation and job enthusiasm as the mediating factor in employees of civil aviation agency offices in Tehran. This study was conducted to investigate the relationship between dynamic personality, job transformation and job satisfaction with job performance. The results showed that the proposed model in all indices has a relatively good fit. Also, the coefficient of direct and indirect paths coefficient is derived. In fact, the existence of a dynamic personality is both directly and indirectly resulting in job performance through transformation of job and job enthusiasm.

Lichtenthaler & Fischbach (2018) conducted a research entitled leadership, job crafting, employee health and function. The purpose of this paper was to integrate the effects of top down leadership and the efficiency of bottom-up employees on health and performance of employees. The results of data analysis showed that promotion of job crafting has a positive effect on employee health and performance. The employee-oriented leadership style also has a positive relationship with job crafting and is not related to its prevention. The mediating role of entrepreneurship promotion in the influence of employee-oriented leadership styles on employees' performance and health was also accepted.

Thun & Bakker (2018) conducted a research titled the enabling leadership and job crafting: its role in employees' optimism. The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between empowerment leadership and job crafting and study the

role of optimism as a personal resource. The results of the structural equation modeling analysis showed that empowering leadership is positively associated with 3 related job strategies (increasing structural employment resources, increasing job resources and increasing job demands), but it will bring in efficiency reduction. Furthermore, as a hypothesis, the optimism enhances the empowering leadership relationship to increase structural resources and the challenging demands. The results showed that the empowering leadership is a significant predictor in job crafting strategies.

Wang, Demerouti & Le Blanc (2017) conducted a research entitled transformational leadership, adaptability and job crafting: The moderating role of organizational cognition. The purpose of this study was to explore the relationship between managerial leadership and job crafting. The results of the structural equation modeling analysis supported some of the research hypotheses. Generally, the findings suggested that transformational leadership was associated with job crafting by resorting to more work spreading activities (searching for resources and challenges) through compatibility, especially for employees with low organizational identification.

Gordon, Demerouti, Le Blanc & Bipp (2015) conducted research entitled the job crafting and performance at the Dutch Healthcare Bases. The results showed that the job crafting affects the performance, but different cultures can displace its impact in different countries and organizations.

The research model was presented as follows:

Figure. 1: Conceptual Model

Source: Lichtenthaler & Fischbach (2018)

METHODOLOGY

In terms of purpose, this is an applied research with survey-descriptive nature. In terms of data type, it is a quantitative research. Also, in terms of analysis method, it was used a correlation method.

The data of this study was obtained by studying the related literature and previous researches in the library method. The employees' opinions were collected by administrating the questionnaires in the field. For sampling, the random sampling method was used. In order to determine the sample size, the total sample was determined by using the Cochran formula at 5% error level. The obtained number of samples was 215 individuals.

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FINDINGS

To investigate the normality of the research variables it was used the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. If the significance of the test is higher than 0.05, the null hypothesis of the variable is accepted, and the variable is normal, and the use of parametric methods is preferable to nonparametric ones.

Table 1: Results from Kolmogorov–Smirnov test

Variable	Test Statistics	Significance	Rejection or Acceptance of null hypothesis	Test Result
Employee leadership oriented	0.21	0.992 ^e	Acceptance of null hypothesis	Variable is normal
Job crafting promotion	0.30	0.859 ^e	Acceptance of null hypothesis	Variable is normal
Prevention of job crafting	0.22	0.988 ^e	Acceptance of null hypothesis	Variable is normal
Performance	0.27	0.930 ^e	Acceptance of null hypothesis	Variable is normal
Employees' health	0.47	0.334 ^e	Acceptance of null hypothesis	Variable is normal

Resource: Author, 2019

According to the mean values of the test, which are all larger than 0.05, the null hypothesis of the test means that the sample distribution is normal at 5% error level and this indicates that there is no significant difference between sample distribution with normal distribution. Therefore, the distribution of the variables is normal and there is a structural equation modeling technique used to implement the structural equation technique.

Prior to factor analysis, the capability of data to perform a confirmatory factor analysis should be investigated. For this purpose, the number of observations and the appropriateness of the observations was investigated. The sample adequacy was examined using the KMO indicator, and if the value of the statistic is over 7.0, the sample size is sufficient with respect to the number of model parameters. In order to ensure the appropriateness of the observations, the Bartlett test was used, and if the test value is less than 0.05, the correlation is suitable.

Table 2. Barteltt Test and KMO Index

Sample Size Adequacy Measurements		Measuring the fitness of correlation (Bartlett)			
Index	Result	Test Statistics	Degree of Freedom	Significance	Result
0.818	The sample size is fit	865/639	190	0.000	Correlation is fit

Resource: Author, 2019

To perform a confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling, it was calculated the standard deviation and t-statistic.

Figure 2. The standard estimation coefficients of the research structural model

Resource: Author, 2019

In other words, the power of the relationship between the factor (latent variable) and the observable variable is represented by factor loadings. The factor loadings are between zero and one. According to the results, the factor loading value of all items is above 0.5.

Figure 3. The values of t statistic test for the research structural model

Chi-Square=224.06, df=160, P-value=0.11000, RMSEA=0.043

Resource: Author, 2019

In the t value or significance state, the model showed t statistics values used to judge the significance of relationships. At the 0.05 error level and two tailed test (normality presumption) the critical values of the numbers were 1.96 and -1.96. The value of statistics analysis test was derived from all items larger than 1.96. Therefore, the item was not removed from the model.

After conducting confirmatory factor analysis, we examined the relationship between research constructs in this stage. For this purpose, the corresponding model was implemented in the LISREL software.

Figure 4. The path coefficient of the independent variable

Chi-Square=237.69, df=164, P-value=0.10200, RMSEA=0.049

Resource: Author, 2019

The path coefficient of the independent variable relied on the dependent variable effect on the dependent variable.

Figure 5. The value of the t-statistic in the influence of the dependent variable on the dependent variable

Resource: Author, 2019

The value of the t-statistic in the influence of the dependent variable on the dependent variable is the measure of rejection or acceptance of an independent variable on the dependent variable. If the absolute value of the statistic obtained from 1.96 is higher, it indicated the significant effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table 3. Summary of the path coefficients

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	t-statistic	Result
Employee oriented leadership has a positive and significant impact on performance.	0.44	3.96	Confirmed
Employee oriented leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee health.	0.23	3.33	Confirmed
The employee-oriented leadership has a positive and meaningful effect on promoting job crafting.	0.42	2.74	Confirmed
The employee-oriented leadership has a negative and significant effect on the prevention of job crafting.	-0.56	-2.56	Confirmed
The promotion of job crafting on performance has a positive and significant effect on performance.	0.36	3.12	Confirmed
Prevention of job crafting has a negative effect on performance.	-0.66	-3.11	Confirmed
the promotion of job crafting on employee health has a positive and significant effect on employees.	0.48	2.41	Confirmed
Prevention of job crafting has a negative and significant effect on employee health.	-0.54	-2.19	Confirmed

Resource: Author, 2019

CONCLUSION

According to the results obtained from data analysis, the employee-oriented leadership influences the propagation and prevention of job crafting. That is, an employee oriented leader can bring about job crafting in organization by his activities such as emphasis on interpersonal relationships as well as the importance of considering the employees' needs, eliminating the obstacles that exist in this direction, as the employee orientalism of a leader by creating a more powerful communication leads to new ways and the creation of new processes that increase the level of job crafting.

In this regard, with more attention and understanding of the position of employees, they better identify obstacles and try to use employees' opinions to address them. Based on data analysis, this leadership style can also improve performance in the organization, Provide the employees with more physical and mental health.

Because if the organization leader understands the position of employees, the attachment of the people to the organization will become more and will work to improve its performance.

The promotion of job crafting in an organization can improve performance by eliminating and repetitive processes and also can take effective steps in building health in employees. Therefore, according to the results, it is suggested that with the theme of changing the style of leadership of organization managers and moving them towards employee orientalism, it is possible to increase job crafting in the organization and experience a better performance. In this regard, we can take effective steps by creating training workshops on employee-oriented leadership and introduction of its components to managers as well as performing comparative studies with successful organizations in this field.

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